

Bilayer coating strategy for glass fiber reinforced polymer composites toward superior fire safety and post-fire mechanical properties

Xiang Ao^{a, b}, Junchen Xiao^{a, b}, Jose Hobson^{a, c}, Jimena de la Vega^{a, b}, Guangzhong Yin^{a, d}, María Luisa Puertas Cuadron^e, Antonio Esteban Cubillo^e, Carlos González^{a, b}, De-Yi Wang^{a*}

^a*IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel, 2, Getafe, Madrid 28906, Spain*

^b*Department of Materials Science, ETS Ingenieros de Caminos, Polytechnic University of Madrid, 28040, Madrid, Spain*

^c*Department of Materials Science and Engineering and Chemical Engineering, Carlos III University, Avda. de la Universidad, 30, 28911 Leganés, Madrid, Spain*

^d*Universidad Francisco de Vitoria, Ctra. Pozuelo-Majadahonda Km 1.800, 28223, Pozuelo de Alarcón, Madrid, Spain*

^e*Tolsa S. A. R. & D. Department, Carretera de Madrid a Rivas Jarama, 35, 28031 Madrid, Spain*

Email: deyi.wang@imdea.org

Abstract

The inherent heat and fire vulnerability from the polymer matrix of fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPs) contributes to fire propagation, matrix decomposition and especially loss of structural integrity during fire hazards. Applying surface fire protective coating is a popular approach without sacrificing mechanical properties. In this work, the influence of fire protective coating on the fire safety and post-fire mechanical properties of FRPs with an ingeniously designed coating bilayer composition. The combustion behavior study showed that the bilayer substantially postpones the decomposition of the polymer matrix through the thickness, showing a reduction of 50% and 65% for peak heat release rate and total smoke production respectively. Fire insulation tests showed good thermal insulation capabilities with no burn-through. Furthermore, the tensile strength of protected composite coupons was screened and showed a retention of 79% original tensile strength after suffering 120s of heat/fire attack. This investigation resulted in a proposed protective

strategy and mechanism offering a meaningful approach to enhancing the fire safety and fire structural integrity of polymer composites.

Keywords: Fiber-reinforced polymer composite; thermal insulation; fire resistance; fire structural integrity

1. Introduction

The lightweight and high-strength properties of fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPs) bring fascinating new choices of materials design^[1] while inevitably imparting issues regarding safety design, especially in terms of fire spread and high-temperature structural loading due to the polymer's inherent ignitability and flammability^[2, 3]. Hence, imparting fire protection properties is vital for the design and usage of FRPs-based structures and artifacts. Flame retardancy generally can be imparted to polymer composites either by physically blending^[4-6], chemically bonding flame retardants (FRs) into the polymer backbone^[7] or applying fire protective coating onto the substrate^[8, 9], as well as fire-retardant sizing on the surface of reinforced fiber^[10, 11].

Liquid composite molding techniques such as vacuum infusion, resin transfer molding etc., have become one of the most widely used manufacturing methods. During this process, adding FR fillers will impart processability of manufacturing, such as viscosity skyrocketing and solid fillers filtration effects^[5]. Incorporating flame retardant elements or groups into the polymer backbone tends to change curing kinetic and processing time as well as decrease thermal-mechanical properties. While surface sizing of FRs onto the fiber surface alters the interface between polymer and fiber, posing a challenge for mechanical

properties. Hence, applying a layer of fire-protective coating stands out among choices with nearly no compromise on the mechanical strength of polymer composites.

Several efforts have been made recently to tackle these challenges. Pomázi et al.^[12] used an APP with an epoxy-based gelcoat to apply a fire-protective coating layer on FRPs. It was found that the use of an additional liquid phosphorus FR to physically blend into the laminate's polymer matrix was needed, which ultimately brought a 67% reduction in peak heat release rate (PHRR) under a 50 kW/m² heat flux of Cone Calorimeter test (CCT). Floch et al.^[13] introduced a poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA)-based coating layer containing ammonium polyphosphate (APP) and sepiolite nanofiller (SP) onto the substrate of glass fiber reinforced polymer composite (GFRP). With SP added in PVA coating with 17 wt.% APP, the temperature on the backside (T_B) of coated composite panel showed a longer plateau at 100 °C and did not undergo self-ignition when tested in vertical position of CCT without forced ignition. It was proposed that the addition of ceramic filler SP improved the thermal barrier effect. Few works also studied the mechanical properties of FRPs after fire damage. Luangtriratana et al.^[14] prepared a vinyl phosphonic acid (VPA) based photo-crosslinked polymer coating layer on the substrate of GRRP. Under autoignition and heat flux of 50 kW/m², the protected laminates remained at 93% of the flexural modulus compared to 73% for laminates without coating after only 30s of heat damage. Later, Luangtriratana et al.^[15] also found that the addition of ceramic particulate containing surface coating helped laminate to retain more flexural modulus after fire damage. While the addition of phosphorus-based coating layer brought down flame retardancy in the early stage of fire hazards, the higher thermal insulation effects derived from ceramic-based materials and the protection of fiber-dominated mechanical properties (such as tensile

properties) is more vital for FRPs in the lateral stage. However, few efforts mentioned above demonstrated both the flame retardancy and avoid loss of mechanical properties after fire.

Hence, we proposed a bilayer coating strategy to impart fire protective properties for FRPs in this work. By introducing intumescent effect on the top layer to bring down fire hazards and introducing ceramification-induced insulative layer for enhancing thermal insulative performance in the later stage of burning, the bilayer strategy was proposed to bring enhanced comprehensive fire-safe performance to FRPs compared to that by traditional single-layer fire protective coating method. First, the multiple fillers-based epoxy coating layers were applied on the laminate's surface. Then, the reaction to fire properties and fire insulation properties were screened by using CCT tests. In addition, the post-fire tensile properties after 120s fire damage were screened to demonstrate the capabilities of protective coatings. Finally, the fire protective mechanism was investigated by multiple measurements, and a theory was proposed, which explained the mechanism of this fire protective coating on the variation of fire safety and post-fire mechanical properties.

2. Results and discussions

2.1. Coating preparation

As shown in Figure 1. The outer coating layer, named ITM layer, was mainly based on the physical intumescent mode flame retardant expandable graphite (EG)^[16], with APP-based and silicate fiber fillers as synergists. The middle layer, named ISU layer, applied directly on the substrate of GFRP laminate, is mainly based on silicon dioxide-based hollow micro glass sphere (HGM) with APP and silicate fibers (Silicate) as synergists. The detailed mass ratio of each fillers in two coating layers were shown in Figure 1. The mass ratio of EG

and APP in ITM layer were chosen according to the experience gained from former work^[17]. The weight ratio of HGM and Silicate was selected as 4:3 according to reference^[18, 19] to achieve idea creamification capacity. The total weight ratios of ternary fillers-based two coating layers were explored and determined with additional consideration of suitable viscosity and good processability to find out the final coating formulations as shown in Table S1.

Figure 1. (a), (c) schematic illustration for the application of bilayer coating on the substrate of GFRP and (b) optical image (i) for the cross-section of coated GFRP. SEM (ii) and EDS images (iii) for the boundary between ITM layer and the ISU layer. SEM (v) and EDS images (vi) for the boundary between the ISU layer and GFRP matrix. (d) Size comparison and detailed weight ratio of different fillers within polymer matrix used in the coating formulation.

As shown in the scheme of Figure 1 (a), the ISU layer was first applied onto the substrate of GFRP laminate, while the ITM layer was then applied above the ISU layer. The fillers used to possess different types of shapes were introduced into the coating polymer matrix,

as shown in Figure S1. According to the optical microscopy image in Figure 1 (b), both two cured coating layers have a dry film thickness of around 1mm. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) mapping also showed a clear boundary between each layer from the element distribution of silicon, validating the successful application of bilayer coating.

2.2. Reaction to fire properties

CCT tests were used to screen the fire reaction properties of composite panels under forced flaming scenarios. As shown in Figure 2 and Table 1, both laminates protected by either one or two coating layers significantly slow the combustion process, as exemplified by two times more combustion time than that of GFRP in Figure 2 (a). The 2mm thick pure gel coat (named Pure coat/GFRP) shows no PHRR lowering and prolonging burning time effects during the combustion process, which indicates pure coat resin even brings higher flammability if no FRs are added. Compared heat release rate (HRR) curves of ITM/GFRP and ISU/GFRP with Pure Coat/GFRP, prolonged burning time indicates slower matrix decomposition and generation speed of combustible volatiles during combustion process.

It is noteworthy that by adding functional fillers into the coating layer, the PHRR and Maximum average rate of heat emission (MARHE) were significantly reduced by more than 50% and 35% for either laminate with one ITM layer or a bilayer of protective coatings, implying an impressive fire protective effect. In addition, in terms of the mass loss curve, the slope value decreased obviously for ITM/GFRP and ITM/ISU/GFRP, as shown in Figure 2 (f). In comparison, the slope value of Pure gel coat GFRP and ISU/GFRP showed nearly no difference compared to that of GFRP. The Pure coat GFRP showed a residue value of around 48%, which was mainly due to the increased mass ratio of combustible

organic resin in the tested sample. The residue value of three coated samples was increased by more than 20% compared to that of Pure Coat/GFRP, indicating the strong char formation and reduction of gasification reaction due to interplay between charring forming effect of APP^[20, 21] and other fillers, as shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. CCT result curves for (a) HRR, (b) SPR, (c) ARHE, (d) THR, (e) TSP, (f) mass versus time.

Due to the incorporation of fillers lowering thermal stability parameters like DTG_{max1} , the time to ignition (TTI) of laminates with the coating layer was earlier than that of GFRP, as exemplified by the results and discussions of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) tests in Table S2, Figure S2, S3. The total heat release (THR) increased as more organic layers were introduced onto the substrate, leading to a higher content of flammable organic substances. As shown in Figure 2 (e) and Figure S4, the total smoke production (TSP) of ITM/ISU/GFRP was lower by 65% and 22% compared to that of GFRP and ITM/GFRP, indicating better fire safety in terms of smoke prevention for the bilayer coating system.

Table 1. CCT results for laminates with no coatings and three different coatings.

Samples	TTI (s)	PHRR (kW/m²)	THR (MJ/m²)	PSRR (m²/s)	TSP (m²)	MARHE (kW/m²)	Residue (wt.%)
GFRP	73	349	38	0.07	4.9	157	68.3
Pure Coat/GFRP	77	669	92	0.09	6.2	282	48.5
ITM/GFRP	50	150	60	0.04	2.2	84	65.4
ISU/GFRP	60	286	56	0.06	3.9	161	60.0
ITM/ISU/ GFRP	46	179	81	0.03	1.7	102	60.0

2.3. Resistance to fire properties

The *in situ* thermal imaging of T_B for composite laminates was employed by using the cone heater in vertical mode as heat resource, as shown in Figure 3 (a). The temperature distribution of the reverse face at different times is shown in Figure 3 (b). The fire quickly consumed all the flammable organic resin in sample GFRP, with burn-through failure occurring in less than 4 min for GFRP. The temperature spike for GFRP in Figure 3 (c) was due to the flame generation at the reverse face after burn-through failure. The temperature profile of the central point of the reverse face showed that ITM/ISU/GFRP showed a value of 184°C maximum difference compared to that of GFRP before burn-through failure. In terms of ITM/GFRP, the intumescent char layer provides good thermal insulation compared to GFRP without any coating protection. At the same time, the consistent irradiant heat provided by the cone heater still induced a burn-through failure after 9 mins of thermal attack, as shown in Figure S5. Nevertheless, the T_B of ITM/ISU/GFRP were kept lower than 300°C for 20 minutes with no burn-through failure until the end of the test. The T_B of ITM/ISU/GFRP showed a maximum difference of almost 90°C compared to that of ITM/GFRP. The digital photos of the tested sample after

the vertical burning test are shown in Figure S6. In conclusion, the bilayer protective coating provided superior fire insulation properties in terms of T_B and avoidance of burn-through failure.

Figure 3. (a) Schematic illustration for the set-up of detecting T_B by thermal camera. (b) thermal images at different times for GFRP, ITM/GFRP, ITM/ISU/GFRP. (c) Centre area temperature versus time curves for GFRP, ITM/GFRP and ITM/ISU/GFRP.

2.4. Charring behavior and structure

The laminate with coating layer after the CCT test displayed a sandwich char structure derived from the bilayer coatings in schematic diagram Figure 4 (a). As shown in Figure S7, char from ITM layer displayed a worm-like porous structure, providing typical insulation effects on heat and mass transfer at earlier stages^[17, 22]. The middle char layer derived from the ISU layer after the CCT test was sampled for SEM measurement in Figure 4 b). The char morphology showed that the HGM sphere, which is linked by substances formed from reactions between silicate fibre and phosphorus agents, is distributed among the char residues. The EDS measurement in Figure 4 (c), (d) of ISU layer char

demonstrated a large presence of oxygen and silicon elements, indicating the creamification process and formation of the inorganic insulating layer^[19].

Figure 4. (a) schematic illustration of the sandwich structure of the char after the test. (b) SEM image and (c), (d) EDS images of ISU layer char after CCT. (e) XRD curves and (f) FTIR curves for fillers and char residues after CCT test. (g) bar chart for tensile strength of GFRP, GFRP120s, and ITM/ISU/GFRP120s. (h) schematic illustration of proposed fire protective mechanism. (i) apparent strain versus apparent tensile stress curves.

XRD and FTIR measurements were employed to explore the char composition and structure. As shown in Figure 4 (e), HGM is an amorphous inorganic filler that showed two broad peaks at 7° and 22° , which still were preserved inside of the two char residues due to its excellent thermal stability. After the combustion or thermal treatment of the ISU layer, the curves of char showed an obvious presence of HGM board peaks. In contrast to the XRD curves of fillers used in formulations, new peaks in char residues were generated

after combustion or thermal treatment, implying a creamification reaction happening during combustion. The FTIR curves of two char residues in Figure 4 (f) showed a strong absorption peak around 1050 cm^{-1} ascribed to the Si-O-Si asymmetric stretching vibration and another absorption peak around 450 cm^{-1} ascribed to the bending vibration of the O-Si-O bond. Due to the low content of two other inorganic fillers in the ISU layer, the new peaks for XRD and FTIR in both char residues were of relatively weak intensities, indicating the creamification process may only take place around the interface between the HGM surface and two inorganic fillers as like the interfacial charring from our previous work^[23].

Based on the results and investigation above, a fire protective mechanism based on the synergistic effects of bilayers is proposed, as shown in Figure 4 (h). Under forced flaming conditions during fire hazard, composite panels with bilayer coatings first reacted to fire with the outer layer turning into a highly porous structure by intumescent effects derived mainly from the interplay of fillers inside of top ITM layers. The EG in top layer quickly reacted with volume expansion after being heated above the onset temperature. Shortly after the initiation of intumescent effects from ITM layer, the interfacial creamification reactions were also happening between the surface of HGM and silicate fillers with the help of phosphorus fillers forming a compact and insulative char structure inside of the ISU layer. The highly porous structure derived from the ITM layer limited thermal and mass transfer, thereby lowering PHRR and TSP and slowing matrix decomposition. However, a single ITM layer-based coating is not enough for limiting thermal transfer at higher temperature range and improving fire resistance properties which are vital for FRPs. The compact char structure derived from ISU coating layer showed a synergistic effect

with ITM layer by enhancing thermal insulation properties and avoiding burn-through effect, which provides further protective capabilities against fire damage.

2.5. Post-fire mechanical properties

The *postmortem* mechanical properties was employed to measure the mechanical properties of FRPS after fire damage. As shown in Figure 4 (g), (i), for GFRP without any protective coating, the 120s heat flux and fire damage brought a hugely detrimental effect on the laminates, resulting in severe delamination between glass fiber layers as well as nearly full consumption of flammable organic resin. The pristine laminates, after the 120s heat attack, leave only non-combustible glass fabric due to rapid decomposition, gasification, and burning of volatiles evolved from resin matrix. Therefore, the tensile behaviour of the GFRP_{120s} displayed very similar behaviour to a dry fabric exhibiting nonlinear deformations caused by yarn undulations during strain straightening. Under the tensile stress, each glass fabric played an individual role without collectively resisting deformation, leaving very low and highly scattered tensile strength results for GFRP_{120s} with a maximum tensile strength of less than 50 MPa. Compared to the tensile strength of pristine laminate, less than 12% of that can be retained after 120s of fire damage, which exemplifies the vulnerability of FRPs to fire without any protection.

The bilayer-coated laminate formed a rigid char residue with good adhesion derived from the ISU layer. The bilayer-coated laminate, after damage, preserved around 79% of the original apparent tensile strength, as shown in Figure 4 (g). In addition, the rigid char residue layer still maintained a good adhesion even under high tensile stress, as shown in Figure S8, indicating the capability of thermal insulation effects under structural loading.

As shown in the inset of Figure 4 (i), the apparent stress-extension curve showed a nonlinear behavior in the traditional elastic region, which differs from the GFRP without fire damage. This may be attributed to the effects of fire protective coating. In this way, the ITM/ISU/GFRP_{120s} can be treated as a non-symmetric sample with gradient strength in the through-the-thickness direction caused by the degradation and, therefore, showing nonlinear tensile behaviour. The drastic strength difference between pristine laminates and protected laminates after 120s of fire damage indicated a highly protective capability derived from the synergistic effect of bilayer coating during combustion process.

3. Conclusions

In this work, a bilayer strategy for fire-protective coating was designed and prepared for FRCs. An intumescent ITM coating layer with a ceramifiable ISU coating layer was deposited on the substrate of GFRP composite laminates. The CCT test showed this bilayer imparted a 50% reduction in PHRR and a 65% reduction of TSP compared to that of GFRP, indicating a lower contribution to fire propagation and poisoning effects under fire hazards. In addition, the *postmortem* tensile test after fire damage indicated strong protective effects on strength perseverance during fire hazards with good adhesion of protective layer even under high structural loadings. The investigations of char residue morphology and compositions by several tests indicated a strong condensing phase protective role contributed by the bilayer during CCT tests, which contributed to the superior post-fire mechanical properties. This bilayer strategy provides a novel perspective for fire safety engineering and the design of polymer composites aiming for the increasingly expanding application of structural loadings among several sectors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xiang Ao: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing-original draft & editing. **Junchen Xiao:** Methodology, Data curation. **Jose Hobson:** Methodology, Data curation. **Jimena de la Vega:** Methodology, Data curation. **María Luisa Puertas Cuadron:** Writing-review & editing. **Antonio Esteban Cubillo:** Writing-review & editing. **Carlos González:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing-review & editing, Supervision. **De-Yi Wang:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing-review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Materials and experimental methods as well as additional figures, tables and discussion can be found in supplementary data.

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